

**PROCEDURAL NON-COMPLIANCE IN THE INDIAN PRISON
ADMINISTRATION SYSTEM AFFECTING THE PRISONER'S RIGHT
TO REHABILITATION- AN OVERVIEW**

by

Aanchal Anand

BBA LLB spec. in International Trade and Investment Laws

University of Petroleum and Energy Studies

Statement of Problem

The primary goal of prison administration should be the rehabilitation of inmates. As a result, prison management should begin rehabilitation as soon as the offenders are placed in jail. During the case of Rama Murthy v. State of Karnataka in 1997, the Supreme Court recognised concerns in prison management such as overcrowding, trial delays, poor health and sanitary amenities supplied to convicts inside jail, and so on, which are impeding the prisoner rehabilitation process. A number of problems that existed in 1990s are still prevailing which is creating the biggest problem. Prisoner rehabilitation is a process that encompasses all aspects of the institution, including the jail itself, the prison staff, and the facilities available to inmates. All of these elements are part of the prisoner reformation and rehabilitation machinery, and if we want this machine to perform well, we must maintain and service it on a regular basis. We need to fund and implement improvements.

We are running prisons with old construction despite the fact that funding is available, prison food has no standards despite the government having the ability to purchase all of the technology and equipment, and people are dumped inside prisons for years despite the fact that all of their legal rights are available to them. Who is not carrying out his responsibilities responsibly? Who is standing in the way of convicts' right to rehabilitation? Where is the genuine problem that we are attempting to identify with our investigation? Despite the fact that the Supreme Court of India has often directed the states and the federal government to enforce human rights in prison, it has not been done.

Research Question

- Why are rehabilitation centres are important for prisoners?
- Whether the prisons made for reformation in the prisoners and sow seeds of rehabilitation is ready for it or not?
- Whether the prisons comply with the disaster management SOPs?

Research Objectives

- To examine the evaluation and development of rehabilitation process
- To conduct a critical analysis of Indian prison administration issues affecting the prisoner rehabilitation process
- To investigate how procedural compliance in Indian prisons affect the rehabilitation process of prisoners

Hypothesis

- The factor of procedural non-compliance is present in Indian prison administration which affects prisoner's rehabilitation
- The existing administration is not sufficient enough to ensure human rights and justice to prisoners.

Research Methodology

Research methodology used in doctrinal and source data is secondary. The content for the research journal has been derived from various articles and books. Also the zest of it has been extracted from books.

Indian Journal of Contemporary Legal and Social Issues

Introduction

The section on procedural non-compliance in Indian prisons explains the reasons for non-compliance with the procedures outlined in the Indian Prison Manual. Only a few of the regular and typical methods are highlighted and addressed in this chapter, which aids us in understanding and analysing difficulties connected to them in a licit manner. The diagram below depicts the key causes of jail overpopulation in India, as well as the consequences of such overcrowding. Two faults are highlighted: the first is the failure to produce detainees before the Court on time, and the second is the mismanagement of the Sub-Jail. As a result of

this problem, some outbreaks have occurred, such as non-compliance with the prisoner quarantine regulation, and the most recent repercussion is the release of prisoners.

Role of three important elements of criminal justice system in respect to process of rehabilitation

Role of Police in the criminal justice system in India¹

- Patrolling and surveillance;
- Making arrests;
- First Information Report;
- Conditional Release of accused on Bond;
- Investigation of Crime;
- Maintenance of Registers;
- To assist Public Prosecutor;

Role of Judiciary in the Criminal Justice System in India

After hearing all of the evidence, the judiciary should render a fair, unbiased, and impartial verdict. The conviction of criminals is another important function of the judiciary.

Role of Prison Administration with regards to the Criminal Justice System in India

The primary role of prison administration with regards to the criminal justice system in India is the rehabilitation of offenders and the transformation of criminals into law-abiding citizens of the country.

Historical Background Of Prison System

Prisons were initially employed to detect and elicit confessions from undertrials. As time passed, both the utilisation of prisons and the conditions within them vastly improved. In prison, new methods of punishment were used, such as reformation, correction, and rehabilitation of convicts. During the 1790s and 1800s, American prison systems like the Pennsylvanian² and Auburn systems experimented with prisoners' rehabilitation. The opening of the Illinois³ jail in 1933 signalled the start of the American prison reform movement. Until the British Parliament passed the Act of 1778, which set the wheels in motion for prison reform in England, the British jail system was cruel and barbaric.

The Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners are a set of rules that govern how inmates are treated. The chairman of the Prison Commission for England and Wales, Sir

¹ Verma Paripurnanand, Crime, Criminal and Convict

² Negley K. Teeters, The Cradles of the Penitentiary (Pennsylvania) prison society

³ Vold. G. B, Theoretical Criminology, 1958

Arthur Waller, proposed to the International Penal and Penitentiary Congress in 1925 that a set of general standards guiding the treatment of inmates in all member countries be put up. Following that, he and his colleague Commissioners were tasked with crafting the Rules. As a result, for the first time, Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners were drafted, and they were recognised by the United Nations following World War II. This prepared the way for broader international discussion on this crucial matter in the coming years. In ancient India, the prison system was well-organized. Manu, on the other hand, was against it.

During the Hindu and Mughal periods in India, the goal of punishment was to dissuade offenders from committing the same act again. Prisoners were ill-treated, tortured, and subjected to the most inhumane treatment during the Mughal era in India, and they were kept under constant monitoring and supervision. During the British colonial rule in India, sufficient measures were taken to eliminate corruption among prison officials. After 1950, India's prison system was governed by the Indian Prison Act of 1894. The Union government has no responsibility for renovating jails or overseeing their management because the Indian Constitution has placed "Jail" and "Police and law and order" in the state list of the Seventh Schedule.

The prison reformation Committees in India

Dr. Reckless was invited to India in 1957 with the goal of preparing a "All India Jail Manual." The following are some of his major recommendations: Correctional services should be an important element of state government, and state prison manuals should be updated on a regular basis. The Justice Mulla Committee⁴ was established in 1980 with the goal of forming a "All India Jail Reforms Committee." The committee recommended that a permanent National Prison Commission be established to bring about "Prison Modernization." The following recommendations were also made by the committee: Improve prison food, sanitation, and ventilation; train prison staff in prison and correctional services; rehabilitation and probation should be an integral part of prison services; the media and general public should be allowed to visit prisons; and the number of undertrials held in jail should be reduced.

Evolution of rehabilitation of prisoners

⁴ Justice Mulla Committee submitted its report on Jail reforms to Home Ministry on 31st March 1983

The International Penal and Penitentiary Commission began work on Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners in 1929, but it failed due to a variety of causes including geographical and political factors. The United Nations, on the other hand, was successful in creating the Standard Minimum Rules in 1949, which can be applied all around the world. The United Nations General Assembly passed the "World Congress on the Prevention of Crime and Treatment of Offenders" in 1955.

According to the Pakwasa Committee's recommendation, a Model Jail was constructed in India in 1949 to foster industrial skills among the prisoners. The foundation of First Women Jail is led by Yerawada Jail in Maharashtra. In Tihar Central Jail and other Indian prisons, a variety of rehabilitation techniques and measures were adopted.

Types of rehabilitation measures undertaken for prison inmates in India

- Development of industrial skills within the prison inmates;
- Open Air Prisons and Community services;
- Development of Values, norms and good culture among prisoners;
- Encouraging prisoners for education;

International and Domestic rights of prisoner

At the international level, international treaties address the rights of prisoners. Following the two world wars, such accords were established.

- The European Conventions on Human Rights,
- United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners,

both relate to human rights and the prevention of torture and cruel or humiliating treatment or punishment⁵.

Prisoners in India do not have all of their fundamental rights, but it does not mean they do not have any. The High Court of Madhya Pradesh has mentioned basic rights that are available to prisoners in the matter of S.P. Anand V. State of Madhya Pradesh, such as standard living

⁵ Prem Shankar Shukla V. Delhi Administration, AIR 1980 SC 1535

space, etc. Prisoner's basic human rights are also available to them while they are incarcerated.⁶ The prohibition on handcuffing, which should only be utilised in rare circumstances and instances, is also an example of the direction in which India's prison rights are moving. Although Article 21 of the Indian Constitution cannot be properly referred to as a prisoner's right, it does offer significant rights to inmates.

The Model Prison Manual, 2016

The Bureau of Police Research and Development created the Model Prison Manual for the Superintendent and Management of Prisons in India. The new Model Prison Manual, 2016 draught has been authorised by authorities and distributed to all states and union territories. The draught contains 32 chapters that address a wide range of prison management challenges, including:-

- Custodial Management;
- Medical care of prisoners;
- Educational and vocational training for prisoners inside prison;
- Skill development programs;
- Legal aid is given to prisoners;
- Visitor rule, etc.

Nonproduction of Prisoners before the Court on Due Date

Under Section 3 of the Prisoners (Attendance in Courts) Act, 1955 state that:

“ When evidence of person confined in prison is material in a matter pending before the court then that person should be brought before Court and for this purpose, the Court issues Order to Officer-in-charge of prison regarding the production of the prisoner before Court. After receiving such order the Officer-in-charge appoints Police Guard or Escort to take the prisoners to the respective court.”

During 2013-17 total of 30,80,940 orders of production of prisoners before courts were issued. 10,56,785 which is 34% of prisoners were not produced before Courts due to non-availability of police Guard/Escort.

In the state of Madhya Pradesh, undertrial prisoners appear in court. Almost 22% of undertrial offenders were not brought to court between 2007 and 2012, resulting in the convicts being denied the right to appear in court. The cause for the delay was that the Jail Superintendent issued the Superintendent of Police a demand for the presentation of undertrial convicts in Court just two to three days before the date of production, causing a delay.⁷

Inspection of Prison by District Magistrate or Additional District Magistrate is an easy solution for the nonproduction of prisoner before the Court. Rule 82 of Jail Manual of Madhya Pradesh State states that a District Magistrate or Additional District Magistrate should conduct an inspection of prison under his jurisdiction once in a month or in inevitable circumstances once in three months. The purpose of this visit is to keep a check in the disposal of Cases and to avoid unnecessary detention of undertrial prisoners for a long period of time.

If a District Magistrate or Additional District Magistrate discovers a delayed case during an inspection, he shall record his findings in the prison's Visitor's Book. The District Magistrate/Additional District Magistrate did not conduct any inspections in 2007-12. There is a shortage of inspection in majority of the prisons in Madhya Pradesh, ranging from 25% to 100%.

Mismanagement of Sub-Jail in India affecting prisoners rehabilitation

What is Sub-Jail (Prison)? What is the purpose of its existence?

Prisoners who commit crimes with the substantive term of imprisonment not exceeding a fortnight or such smaller term only are kept in the sub jails. Prisoners undergoing imprisonment for more than 14 days are transferred to either District or Central prison, but it was stated in Audit that a larger number of prisoners are kept in Sub-Jail for a period of more than 6 months to 53 months.

To understand Sub-mismanagement, it is necessary to first understand Sub-operation. jail's The management and supervision of the Sub-Jail are divided into two departments. To begin, the Sub-Jail is administered by Revenue Authorities, who are assisted by the Inspector General of Police. The second phase, monitoring, is overseen by the Prison Department. There are

⁷ Report of the Comptroller and Auditor General of India ON GENERAL AND SOCIAL (NON-PSUs) SECTORS for the year ended 31 March 2012, Government of Madhya Pradesh Report No 4 of the year 2013, Page 21

currently 628 Sub-Jails in India, with a total capacity of 44,916 convicts, but the current inmate population is 36,775 with an occupancy rate of 81.9 percent. 18.1 percent of India's Sub-Jail capacity is underutilised. There are 102 Sub-Jails in Maharashtra, 54 of which are operational and the remaining 48 are inactive.⁸.

The reason behind Non-Functioning of Sub-Jails are as follows:

- Lack of funds provided by IGP to Revenue Department;
- Most of the Sub-jails are old construction, therefore, it compromises on safe custody of prisoners;

Other issues of Sub-Jails are:

- No appointment of Prison Official is made in the Sub-Jails;
- Sub-Jails are handled by the inexperienced staff of the Revenue Department with no knowledge about prison administration;
- In Maharashtra State Sub-Jails there was no inspection conducted in 5 years (2013-18);
- No proper utilization of Sub-Jails which results in overcrowding of District and Central Prison. Due to overcrowding in prison, the administration could not enforce the rule of quarantine of the prisoners at the time of their admission.

Non-Compliance of Prisoners Quarantine Rule

What is the Prisoners Quarantine Rule? What is the Reception Unit?

The prisoner quarantine regulation states that when a prisoner is admitted, he or she must spend at least 10 days in a Reception Unit to familiarise themselves with the prison environment. The reception units are used to keep inmates quarantined while they are being processed into prison. Only four jails in Madhya Pradesh have a Reception Unit, while the remaining 28 do not. The lack of availability of Reception Units is related to prison overcrowding. Savings in budget allocation and expenditure are being highlighted by the Madhya Pradesh government as a beneficial aspect of administration⁹.

⁸ Report of the Comptroller and Auditor General of India on General and Social Sector for the year ended March 2018, GOVERNMENT OF MAHARASHTRA Report No. 1 of the year 2019, Page 41

⁹ Report of the Comptroller and Auditor General of India ON GENERAL AND SOCIAL (NON-PSUs) SECTORS for the year ended 31 March 2012, Government of Madhya Pradesh Report No 4 of the year 2013, Page 51

Sr No.	Scheme	Saving	Percentage
1	Modernisation in Jail Administration	0.17 crore	39 %
2	Jail Improvement Scheme of GOI	0.75 crore	50 %
3	Modernisation of Jails of GOI	0.35 crore	56 %

The purpose of these funds is to develop prison administration but from saving column it reflects that utilization of funds is slow which creates an indirect effect on prison development resulting in non-compliance of rules by the prison administration. The absence of a disaster management plan is also an area at which this state government should focus before presenting savings of funds provided for redevelopment of prison.

Absence of Disaster Management Plan for Prisons in India

Supreme Court Of India, Suo Motu Writ Petition (C) No. 1/2020 In Re: Contagion of COVID-19 Virus in Prisons: 16.03.2020, Supreme Court of India issued notice to all the States and UTs and instructed them to show cause why directions should not be issued for dealing with the present health crisis arising out of Coronavirus (COVID-19) concerning Prisons and Remand Homes; Many States & UTs filed their response; Supreme Court after looking into the possible threat of transmission of COVID-19 into prison directed States & UTs to constitute a “High Powered Committee”;

High Powered Committer Members;

- Chairman of the State Legal Service Committee;
- The Principal Secretary (Home/Prison);
- Director-General of Prison

Purpose of the High Powered Committee was to determine which class of prisoners can be released on interim Bail or parole for an appropriate period to reduce overcrowding in prison; Supreme Court recommends the following categories of the prisoner for consideration of release;

- Prisoners who are convicted/undertrial for one offense for which the sentence is up to seven years;

- Any categories identified by the High Powered Committee based on the nature of the offence, duration of the sentence and severity of the offence;

The Supreme Court also directed the High-Powered Committee to consider the directions in the case "Arnesh Kumar V. State of Bihar (2014) 8 SCC 273"; the Supreme Court also directed States and UTs to develop a disaster management plan; and statistics of prisoners to be released by the state due to the outbreak of Corona Virus in India during the year 2020 are 66,661 estimated numbers of prisoners to be released in India, compared to 4,66,084 total number of prisoners in India at the moment. The necessity for prisoner release and a Disaster Management Plan for India jails stems from the fact that inmates are vulnerable and underrepresented, and they lack the flexibility to make independent decisions to protect themselves from disasters.

Board of Visitors in Maharashtra State

A Board of Visitors should be created for each prison in Maharashtra, according to Rule 3 of the Maharashtra (Visitors to Prison) Rule 1962. The members of the Board of Visitors are as follows: Non-official Members, such as distinguished persons from the field of penitentiary administration and juvenile welfare, and Ex-officio Visitors, such as Presidency Magistrates, Session judges, District Magistrates, Commissioners¹⁰

Board of Visitors responsibilities are:

- Inspection of Barracks;
- Ascertaining of health,
- cleanliness and security of prisoners;
- Examine registers of convicted and undertrial prisoners;
- Hearing and attending all petitions and representations withheld by the Superintendent under rules in force be forwarded to the State Government.

In the State of Maharashtra, out of 54 prisons only in 14 prisons, Non-official members are appointed.

Conclusion

¹⁰ Report of the Comptroller and Auditor General of India on General and Social Sector for the year ended March 2018, GOVERNMENT OF MAHARASHTRA Report No. 1 of the year 2019, Page 67

The majority of procedural non-compliance in Indian prisons focuses on overcrowding, the reasons that contribute to congestion, and the consequences of overcrowding. In a developed state like Maharashtra, 34% of convicts were denied the right to have their cases heard in court. The state of Madhya Pradesh, for example, has 22% of undertrial convicts waiting to be brought before the court. The lack of police guards who will transport these undertrial convicts to the Court is a regular reason for such a delay. The right to rehabilitation begins the moment a prisoner enters the facility, but the right to be heard is delayed due to a shortage of workers.

In India, the sub-jail system is undervalued and mismanaged. The Sub-strength Jail's is not fully utilised, as it has the ability to lessen jail congestion in India if administered effectively and efficiently. The prisoner quarantine rule was created with the sole purpose of acclimating prisoners to prison and its culture, but due to overcrowding and a lack of Reception Units, prisoners are thrown into an environment that kills the sole purpose of prison, which is to rehabilitate prisoners, and turns it into a race to get out as soon as possible.

Recommendations & Suggestions

The solution must be practical, cost-effective, and socially acceptable. The prison must be built and maintained according to a set of well-defined standards. The prison construction should be constructed to give all of the required amenities for convicts to be regarded as human beings and to be housed in an atmosphere that is conducive to their reformation. Following are some recommendations based on this ideology:

Recommendation No. 1: Boost the number of police guards and warders.

A person's right to be admitted to a hospital during a period of illness exists regardless of whether or not he or she is a prisoner. However, because prisoners have no right to freedom of movement in and out of prison, the prison authorities is completely responsible for their health. However, it has been discovered that many prisons fail to transport sick inmates to hospitals due to a lack of police officers and warders.

Recommendation No. 2: In India, the District Magistrate/Additional District Magistrate should review jails on a regular basis.

The goal of the inspection done in prison by a District Magistrate/Additional District Magistrate is to check on the disposition of cases in order to avoid the unnecessary detention of undertrial convicts for a long period of time.

Recommendation No. 3: Effective Sub-Jail Management

In India, Sub-jail is run by Revenue authorities who have no experience in prison administration; as a result, convicts are forced to spend long periods of time in Sub-jail, which is against prison lodging policy. Transfer of management of the Sub-jail from the inexperienced employees of the revenue department to the prison authority is a pressing need, since the Sub-jail has a lot of potential to handle the overcrowding of prisons that is primarily carried by District and Central Prisons in India. To transfer such a crucial authority, we need people who are specially trained to handle such tasks therefore appointment of Prison Official in Sub-Jail should be carried out to put this candidate back on track who will play a vital role in the reduction of overcrowding in prison. Two major tasks should be undertaken. Firstly, transfer of management of Sub-jail to prison authority from revenue authority and secondly appointment of Prison officials in Sub-Jail in India.

Recommendation No. 4: Establish Reception Units in all Indian prisons to implement the Prisoner Quarantine Rule.

Reception Units assist inmates in acclimating to prison and its culture; yet, when Reception Units are not available, the prisoner is exposed to a harsh world of imprisonment in which the true goal of their imprisonment is lost in the midst of it all. Before being placed in jail, inmates should always be introduced to Reception Units. To put the prisoner quarantine law into action, all Indian prisons must establish Reception Units.

Recommendation No. 5- Disaster Management Plan for Indian Prisons

Prisoners are particularly vulnerable and underrepresented in society. Prisoners lack the freedom to make their own decisions on how to safeguard themselves in the event of a calamity. We can't foretell what will happen in the future, but we can prepare for it. The first step in being prepared for any future calamity is to create a disaster management plan. The Disaster Management Plan lays forth the criteria that decision-makers must follow in the event of a crisis, reducing the disaster's impact. However, because to the lack of a crisis management plan for prisons, Indian governments are being forced to make the difficult decision of releasing criminals on interim bail or parole as a result of the COVID-19 outbreak in Indian prisons. To

deal with such situations in the future, a disaster management strategy for prisons is urgently needed, as it will secure the safety of prisoners and the rehabilitation process.

The Propose Disaster Management Plan for Indian Prison. This Plan is divided into three important stages. The first stage is Planning and Coordinating, the second stage is Rapid Response Team formation and functions and the third stage is Medical Facility procurement and supply management.

Stage 1 – Planning & Coordinating

- Alert and informed staff and prisoners about the disaster;
- Risk assessment;
- Ensures representation of women prison administrators in decision making in response against disaster;
- Idea mapping & physical re-planning of the sites;

Stage 2 – Rapid Response Team Formation and Functions;

- Surveillance;
- Case Identification, investigation, and reporting;

Stage 3 – Medical Facility procurement and supply management;

- Stocking of Medical & hygiene supplies on calculated bases;
- Keep Ambulance and Fire services on standby;
- A fire drill shall be conducted every 6 months consistent with the security requirements of prison.

Recommendation No. 6: Both my government and its members should take the role of the Board of Visitors more seriously.

Ex-officio visitors and Non-official Members make up the Board of Visitor, which is charged with inspecting the jail, prisoner health, and sanitation facilities, as well as examining all prison procedural compliances. However, because the Board is not run on a serious note, both visitors and the appointor of the Board must take the board and its operations more seriously.

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Indian Journal of Contemporary
Legal and Social Issues